

Ganigas: Condition of Cold Pressed Oil Industry

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Abstract: India is a vast country and the inhabitants of several of its regions have developed specific preference to certain oils among the oils available in the region. For example, people in the south and west prefer groundnut oil while those in the east and north use rapeseed oil. Likewise several segment in the south have a preference for coconut and sesame oils. The economic prosperity of a country like India depends upon the development of agriculture and cottage industry in a balanced manner and it reveals the importance of agriculture in the process of industrial development. The growth of organized industrial sector in the country was started with the development of agro based industries. Oil pressing, in view of its large potential, is now regarded as the sunrise sector of the Indian economy for growth and also exerts a great socio-economic impact specifically on employment and income generation. If properly developed, Oil pressing sector can make India a major player at the global level for marketing and supply of processed food, and feed a wide range of other plant and animal products. Most of the agro processing industries are traditional, cottage-based and small scale and among them, oil mills occupy a predominant place in India. The review of literature reveals that, the studies associated with the prospects and problems of Ganniga community in Karnataka in general and in particular are very low, and the studies associated with oil milling industry either in Karnataka are nil. It is a traditional oil expeller used by people of Ganiga in districts of Karnataka. It is a simple traditional technology widely distributed in the rural areas. The traditional oil press is used for extraction of oil by a particular community Ganiga who are the oil expeller and oil selling community in Karnataka.

Key words; Ganigas, oil, Industry, condition, socio-economic, Status Etc..

Introduction:

Ganigas basically belongs to Cold pressed oil trade called "Gaana". This is a trade based Community and considered trade as its soul. Once this was fore front industry among all the Cottage Industries. These bull driven oil Extractors, extracted the oil and fulfilled the need of pure oil to the locals and the people around the villages every day. Earlier the Ganigas were in joint family and the few family members were doing Gaana work and others used to travel, distribute and sell the Oil. Ganiga Community found in various states of India like Karnataka, Andrapradesh, Tamilnadu, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Bihar, Orissa, Bengal, Uttarpradesh. They were called by different names in different regions as Gandla in Andrapradesh, Chattiya and Chatte in Kerala, Vaniyan in Tamilnadu, Teli in Maharashtra and Gujarat, Saho in Bihar and Orissa, Guptas in Uttarpradesh and Madyapradesh, Jyothi in Bengal, Ganigas, Jyothi, Teli in Karnataka (Rajashekarappa M:2019:21). In Karnataka we can find Four sub categories in Ganiga Community as Sajjana Ganiga, Jyothi ganiga, Enne ganiga and Kariganiga. This is a widely spread community and it is our dire need to know how this vast community has gone far away from its main trade and also the condition of cold pressed oil industry or Gaana Udyama. There was a time when this Ganiga Community has provided oil to the entire society when there was no oil industry and converted machines.

Now we have to study how this community doing for its living and which alternative trade is following when it is left the Industry. Besides we also have to find whether this 'Gaana' industry is still existed or not. It's our responsibility to understand the Trade based Community.

Ganigas means : trade based Community. The process of oil making by using wooden or stone, oil mills are operated by a pair of bullocks and the people who extracted oil by this way are called as Ganigas.

Industry means: people and activities involved in producing goods. Industry is an organization and the persons who runs it called as an industrialist. The trade which is done for the sake of livelihood is also called as industry or Udyama.

What is Gana Industry? The people who extracts oil is a called Ganigas and that trade is called Gaanada Udyama. The people who extracts oil and sells its to the villages are identified as Ganigas or who provides best quality oil are also called as Ganigas.

Hypothesis

Social and Economically Ganigas well of from Oil industry

In modernity the original profession of Ganigas has disappeared

Purpose Of Study

To understand the Condition of Gaanada Industry

To find the Ganigas who involved in the industry and confront them with the Society

To Confront the Traditional Gaana with Modernization

To find the other Communities who are Practicing and Involved in this Industry except Ganigas.

Review of Literature

Thimmareddy S.Y., Kula kasubugalu mattu Adunikathe, Essay which is Submitted for Ph.D

Gaanagarike, the trade which is extracting oil from the oil seeds was existed before Vijayanagara Empire and it was also an important trade. Ganigas were there in all parts of the empire. And they are called as Hegganigas and Kiruganigas. Ganas were divided as Maragana and Kallugana. The oil was extracted from Hucchellu, Haralu, Kobbari, Hippe and Honge seeds. The cold compressed oil or Gaana Industry was so prominent that the tax was recovered by collecting money or Oil.(72:2010)

Vasudevan C.S.(A) 'Shasonokta ennenadu', Bhatsuri K.G.(e) 2006, Shasana Adyayana Samputa 3, Sanchike 2, Prasara Kanna university, Hampi, P.73-7.

"Few Edicts of Mysore and Chamarajanagara mentions Ennenadu, ennestala, and Ennenadu"(Va:2006:P:73). It is significant that the places in Ennenadu starts with 'HA(ಹೆ). For Example Haradanahalli, Harulukote, Handrahalli etc. May be these villages come from 'haralu'. Haralenne (Castor oil) is extracted from Haralu (Castor) seeds. Thereby the places of these regions starts with Ha (ಹೆ), means we can opine that the villages are named after the raw material used to extract the oil.(Vasudevan: 2006:P:75). In this article they have acknowledged the Edicts which belongs to Ennenadu or land of Oil shows how prominent the Gana Industry was.

SCOPE

Scope means the extent of the area or range. We should have a range when we involved in any studies. Here we have opted selected villages in various districts of Karnataka and only the Ganiga trade for our study.

Importance

Once the community which produced oil made it as an industry. We can explore how Industrial revolution made the Ganigas to leave their trade, why they have chosen an alternative trade, their condition. And also through this kind of study we can expect the progress of Ganiga Community.

Modes of Study

We have studied and reviewed articles, books essays to prepare the article about Present condition of Ganada Udyama or Cold

Compressed oil Industry. Also chosen situational data and simple random information along with questionnaire method.

Condition

Condition means a state of something, time means duration or process. Duration means the length of time one thing tasks to be completed.

The Process of Condition of Gana Industry

Ganigas lived by selling extracted oil. Their life is solely depended on Gana Industry. Once they are as known as cooking oil. People gives much respect to these ganigas who supplies varied cooking oils. They are called as ganiga shetru, oil extractors, ganada maneyavaru, and the woman from ganiga families are called by names ganagittiyaru, ganadodatiyaru and ganada maneyaki. Ganigas were well known in the localities that people used to come and talk to them wherever they are in those days. When there were no electric Lights, 5 feet Pole was built and ganigas used to provide oil to this pole in the evening. The extracted oil was sent to gram panchayat or village leaders. The entire village was lit by the oil given by them. Brahmims in Agraharas used to uy haralenne and ellene for temples to lit the lamps. There was a huge demand for oil from ganigas, and also we can find the edicts which informs that the kings also given ganas as gift/charity to temples to extract oil for lamps. Ganigas were financially stable during those days when the whole ganiga family is appointed for temple to manage those ganas and the suitable wages also given to their labor. The neem oil was huge in demand because of its medicinal values. The cows were the backbone of this industry and the neem oil plays a vital role in their protection. Kalu bai roga, charma turike diseases are resolved by this neem oil and some of the human diseases and wound were also cured by adding turmeric to neem oil. In those days tractors and advanced technologies were not there, cows are used for sowing it. To protect these cows people were in queue in front of ganigas house to buy the oil and hindi. Hindi is good for cattles and they give quality milk so that people pays the money to reserve the food in advance to protect the farms from the diseases like boodu roga and seede roga they used to mix the Hindi in water and sprinkles in the farm. The farm gives good yielding by this, Not only the oil but also the hindi() was useful.

Gaana may be a trade but we can also find many uses. Ganigas were making their livelihood by extracting oil from Ganas. As Population increased in India the government made a Pcat and started to import Palm oil or Tale Enne from The Arab Countries in 70's and 80's for over

Twenty years. The Compressed Oil industry came to extinct in these days. The imported palm oil was just 20/- per litre whereas Compressed oil is 40/-. People started to buy the oil which is very low in price. No one was asking about oil produced from the Ganas. They started to buy the palm oil which is available at cheap cost. When the things are not going well they left their trade. The ganas which are used for trade purpose now only meant for Pooja Ritual. They could not get a single penny through this. The community which was paying tax now lost its breadwinning hands. They started new trades like textile showrooms, Provisional stores, general stores.. They invested their left amount and started a new life by selling readymade oil pockets and newly transformed cold pressed oil. The newly transformed oil mills, pocket oils and oil factories shook away the very existence of Gaanigas and Gana Industries. They couldn't compete with the modern oil Producing machines. Once highly demanded Cold pressed oil industry and the Gaaniga community has vanished because of pocket oils. They have

reached the zenith from nadir due to the modernisation of oil industries and machines.

TABLE: The details of traditional Enne ganas in present Day

When we observe the above table, can find the community which is largely involved in Oil production. Here all the communities have given importance to Tradition Enne gana or Cold compressed oil. Mainly the ganiga community is trying to preserve and save the trade. This way ganigas and ganas are again flourishing. The unheard sound of ganas are hearing everywhere now. The increase in the incurable diseases also lead a way to the flourishing of this industry and it has been working as a remedy to those diseases. Many people who are suffering from cough, blood pressure, diabetes, arthritis are using the oil which is produced by cold compressed industry or gaana. Now people have a opinion that the industry is again came into light and the stone and wooden gaanas are in use. It has given financial stability to the ganigas who solely depends on this industry. Besides with ganigas many other communities are practising this.

Sl no	Community	Stone gana	Wooden gana	Transformed gana	Others	Total
1	Ganigaruru	7	3	8	4	32
2	Goudalu	2	1	3	Nil	06
3	Rajaparivara	Nil	1	Nil	Nil	01
4	Muslim	Nil	Nil	02	01	03
5	Lingayata	04	02	02	01	09
Total		13	17	15	06	51

Research Outcomes

Once the condition of Compressed Oil Industry was completely devastated but now its gradually raising its head.

Can maintain a family by a Ganada Udyama
 Earlier we can find 2 to 3 ganas now a days we could not find that.

Can find ganigas are reestablishing Gana industries again.

Ganigas' opines that they Can save the traditional age old oil industries

Oil is extracting through Stone, wood, and transformational form.

Others are also involved in the industry along with ganigas.

Most of the ganas are used for pooja ceremony only.

Suggestions: Government should encourage and facilitate the People who are running gana industries.

Government and organization has to come forward to save the Gana industry which is cottage industry.

Should encourage and develop wood and stone ganas

Create awareness among the youth about Enne gana trade

Should incorporate value based texts that includes social sensibility and conservation of basic trade.

Conclusion: On the whole we can say that the Ganada udyama or Industry has extinguished. Many people did not have the aware of Ganas and did not know Gana means Enne gana or oil extracting. They thought that gana means (Bellada) Jaggery gana or Sugar cane gana . Now the scenario is changing and the gana industry is breathing again. It has came into light because of people's much care and concern towards health, and it is a matter of joy that the Ganigas are trying hard to preserve and protect their trade and gana industry . They are creating opportunities and space to lead their life easier with the help and development of Gana industry. They are trying to confront the old age trade with new modern world and technology.

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